

APPENDIX F
Performance of each method

Table F.1
Sequential method

Plan (Actions)	Time for calculating the plan for each test								
	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Test 6	Test 7	Test 8	Test 9
Plan 1 (3 Actions)	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000
Plan 2 (4 Actions)	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,5024	0,5011	0,5005	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000
Plan 3 (5 Actions)	0,0000	0,5011	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,5005	0,0000	0,0000
Plan 4 (6 Actions)	0,0000	0,5011	0,0000	0,5005	0,0000	0,5011	0,0000	0,0000	0,5018
Plan 5 (7 Actions)	0,0000	0,0000	1,0036	0,4986	0,0000	0,5017	0,0000	0,0000	0,5011
Plan 6 (8 Actions)	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,5030	1,0016	0,0000	0,0000
Plan 7 (9 Actions)	0,5024	0,5011	0,0000	2,0052	0,5018	0,0000	0,4998	0,5024	0,5044
Plan 8 (10 Actions)	0,5018	0,0000	0,5005	0,5012	1,0016	0,5011	0,0000	1,0009	0,0000
Plan 9 (11 Actions)	1,0023	0,5005	0,4985	0,5005	0,4980	0,5012	0,4998	1,0016	0,5011
Plan 10 (12 Actions)	1,5008	0,5011	0,4973	0,5030	0,4998	0,5005	0,5005	0,5011	0,5024
Plan 11 (13 Actions)	1,5022	1,5034	0,0000	0,5005	0,4992	0,5037	1,0004	1,5021	0,5018
Plan 12 (14 Actions)	0,5005	1,0010	0,4979	0,4986	0,5012	1,0042	0,4986	0,5005	0,5024
Plan 13 (15 Actions)	1,5041	0,5012	0,5012	0,5030	0,5018	0,5005	0,4979	0,5018	0,5011
Plan 14 (16 Actions)	1,0029	0,5018	0,5012	0,5024	0,4980	1,5015	0,4985	0,5012	0,4992
Plan 15 (17 Actions)	0,9978	0,5024	1,0029	0,5011	2,0032	0,5005	0,4998	1,0010	0,5005
Plan 16 (18 Actions)	0,5011	0,5005	0,4986	0,5005	1,0048	1,0023	0,5011	0,5004	2,0019
Plan 17 (19 Actions)	0,4998	0,4999	1,0010	1,0004	1,0029	0,4999	0,5024	1,0023	1,5021
Plan 18 (20 Actions)	0,4998	2,0051	0,5011	0,5005	0,5005	1,0004	0,5011	0,5005	1,0010
Plan 19 (21 Actions)	0,5011	0,5011	1,0017	0,5050	1,0042	2,0026	1,0010	1,0022	2,0013

Table F.2
Muise's method

Number of actions	Time for calculating the plan for each test								
	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Test 6	Test 7	Test 8	Test 9
Plan (Actions)	6,01	6,51	5,51	6,01	6,51	5,50	5,51	6,01	6,51
Plan 1 (3 Actions)	26,46	6,51	6,51	8,01	7,01	6,52	7,01	27,04	7,01
Plan 2 (4 Actions)	42,99	8,01	8,01	7,75	7,51	8,51	8,51	23,04	22,04
Plan 3 (5 Actions)	28,55	30,05	10,02	9,51	30,55	9,51	9,51	10,52	28,04
Plan 4 (6 Actions)	13,02	42,57	32,05	14,02	14,52	38,56	38,56	13,52	32,55
Plan 5 (7 Actions)	57,59	39,56	21,03	20,53	20,03	40,57	20,03	20,03	20,53
Plan 6 (8 Actions)	34,06	34,06	54,09	34,56	57,09	36,56	55,12	98,66	53,66
Plan 7 (9 Actions)	138,29	80,13	77,66	97,71	78,67	77,63	59,10	76,69	77,04
Plan 8 (10 Actions)	259,15	139,73	152,25	134,72	151,25	133,21	151,24	132,21	169,77
Plan 9 (11 Actions)	249,44	251,16	335,20	250,91	300,82	372,97	252,47	314,84	260,45
Plan 10 (12 Actions)	517,22	513,38	630,68	484,60	766,38	519,25	515,14	495,24	728,45
Plan 11 (13 Actions)	976,20	1279,60	943,08	1327,49	1277,82	1354,03	981,06	915,70	1169,86
Plan 12 (14 Actions)	2218,07	2415,58	2532,65	2373,27	2310,23	2654,35	2515,22	2143,81	2589,05
Plan 13 (15 Actions)	4691,71	3771,58	5069,29	4516,12	4825,84	3833,76	3802,53	4815,49	3749,34
Plan 14 (16 Actions)	8820,46	9759,23	9118,82	8307,42	7855,91	8075,68	8283,52	8229,26	9501,67
Plan 15 (17 Actions)	16737,74	18676,62	17581,18	16733,75	19328,31	17307,07	18964,62	16672,60	17903,84
Plan 16 (18 Actions)	34246,84	34190,17	35841,27	31973,38	35505,94	34500,73	33058,53	34660,46	35175,22
Plan 17 (19 Actions)	64285,18	64597,30	63898,86	61231,13	64093,09	70519,44	66392,15	66890,01	62472,63
Plan 18 (20 Actions)	131784,62	129194,59	112238,17	119603,72	128186,17	141038,88	119505,88	127091,03	131192,53

Table F.3
Proposed method

Number of actions	Time for calculating the plan for each test								
	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Test 6	Test 7	Test 8	Test 9
Plan (Actions)	3,00	3,01	2,50	9,02	9,52	3,00	9,02	3,00	3,00
Plan 1 (3 Actions)	3,01	3,00	3,50	3,00	3,00	3,00	9,01	3,50	4,01
Plan 2 (4 Actions)	3,00	3,51	3,50	4,04	3,00	10,52	3,00	3,51	3,86
Plan 3 (5 Actions)	4,51	3,51	4,01	9,52	4,01	4,01	4,00	3,51	9,52
Plan 4 (6 Actions)	4,51	5,01	5,01	4,54	5,01	4,51	5,51	16,53	5,51
Plan 5 (7 Actions)	10,02	10,52	3,50	4,51	3,51	3,01	10,52	3,51	3,51
Plan 6 (8 Actions)	4,01	3,51	4,01	4,51	4,01	3,50	11,52	4,01	4,01
Plan 7 (9 Actions)	18,03	5,01	5,51	5,01	5,01	6,02	6,01	5,51	5,51
Plan 8 (10 Actions)	5,51	18,03	5,51	5,51	5,51	5,01	5,34	6,01	5,51
Plan 9 (11 Actions)	4,51	4,01	4,01	4,51	4,00	4,51	5,01	4,01	5,51
Plan 10 (12 Actions)	4,51	21,54	6,01	6,01	7,01	6,01	6,01	9,01	5,51
Plan 11 (13 Actions)	11,52	4,01	4,01	3,50	11,02	4,01	4,01	4,01	4,00
Plan 12 (14 Actions)	4,01	3,50	4,51	12,52	4,51	6,01	12,52	4,51	4,51
Plan 13 (15 Actions)	13,02	4,01	4,01	4,51	4,51	4,01	4,01	4,01	4,51
Plan 14 (16 Actions)	4,51	4,51	4,01	12,52	4,01	5,01	5,01	4,01	5,01
Plan 15 (17 Actions)	4,01	4,51	4,01	4,00	4,01	13,02	4,01	4,01	12,02
Plan 16 (18 Actions)	4,01	4,51	5,01	12,02	4,51	4,01	4,51	5,51	13,52
Plan 17 (19 Actions)	4,51	4,01	4,01	4,54	14,02	5,01	13,02	4,04	4,01
Plan 18 (20 Actions)	23,54	7,01	7,01	6,51	19,03	6,51	24,04	24,04	7,01